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A new species of *Allotyphlus* Coiffait, 1955 (Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Leptotyphlinae) from Greece

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SUMMARY. New leptotyphline species, *Allotyphlus (Moreotyphlus) karamani* sp. n. is described and illustrated from Peloponnese, Greece.

KEY WORDS: Entomoculiini, *Moreotyphlus*, Peloponnese, taxonomy.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Allotyphlus* Coiffait, 1955 has currently 24 valid species names. The genus is assigned into two subgenera: *Allotyphlus* (s.str.) with 8 species known from Italy (2) and Greece (6 species in Kerkyra and Lefkada), and *Moreotyphlus* Coiffait, 1959 with 12 species from Italy (3) and Greece (9 species from Epiros, Crete, Kephhalonia and Peloponnese). Four species, three from Turkey and one from Greece are assigned to *Allotyphlus* incertae sedis. Greece, with 16 described species, is a centre of the diversity of the genus.

Three species of the subgenus *Moreotyphlus* have been currently known from Peloponnese, namely *A. patrensis* Coiffait 1959, *A. naupliensis* Coiffait 1959 and *A. spartensis* Coiffait 1959. As usual, all known members of the subfamily Leptotyphlinae, also all species of *Allotyphlus*, are typical soil-dwellers and inhabit upper soil horizons.

The members of the genus are externally very uniform and they can be distinguished only by the study of the male genitalia. The aedeagus is always very characteristic and provides stable characters for the correct identification on the species-level and thus its proper examination is inevitable.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All collected specimens were preserved in 70% ethanol and afterwards prepared. The aedeagus was removed by dissection and embedded on a microscopic slide

in PVP (polyvinylpyrrolidone) without a coverslip. The drawings were prepared at a magnification of 800x with Zeiss Axiolab microscope with 20x oculars from Euromex. Additional description was done with Euromex D-series binocular. All specimens and the aedeagus were mounted on a classic mounting card in PVP.

DEPOSITORIES

MMBC Moravian Museum, Brno, Czech Republic

PCDP private collection of Dragan Pavićević, Belgrade, Serbia

PCTS private collection of Tim Struyve, Brussels, Belgium

TAXONOMY

Allotyphlus (Moreotyphlus) karamani sp. n. Figs 1-2

MATERIAL STUDIED: Holotype ♂: Greece: Pelopponese: Mani: Gytheo: Platanos, 18.04.2022, leg. I. Karaman, 36.773652°N, 22.485221°E (MMBC). Paratypes (3♂, 4♀): same data as for holotype (PCDP, PCTS).

DESCRIPTION. Body (Fig. 1) reddish-brown, 1.05-1.15 mm (abdomen extended) long, length of forebody (front margin of head without mandibulae until posterior margin of the elytra) 0.4 mm.

Head as large as the pronotum, with strong microsculpture and some scattered punctures; false ocelli visible as two dark spots on centre of head. Antennae long, scape slightly longer than wide; pedicel about as long as wide and as wide as scape; antennomeres 3-10 strongly transverse; antennomeres, 3, 4 and 6 subequal, about 0.60 times as wide as scape; antennomeres 5 and 7 subequal, about 0.75 times as wide as scape and twice as wide as long; antennomeres 8 and 9 gradually larger, about twice as wide as long, antennomeres 9 and 11 as wide as scape; antennomere 10 slightly wider compared with 9 and 11 and slightly longer than twice as long as wide (5/8), antennomere 11 as long as wide; antennal club weakly-defined, composed of 3 last antennomeres.

Pronotum about 1.2 times as long as wide, largest just in front of anterior angles, evenly convergent posteriorly; posterior margin rounded; microsculpture reduced to traces and some scattered punctures.

Elytra as wide as pronotum, slightly shorter than wide (about 0.13 mm long), narrowest near anterior margin; microsculpture reduced to traces and some scattered punctures; lacking foveae or striae.

Abdomen gradually widening up to visible tergite 5 (VII), here about 0.18 mm wide; well-defined microsculpture starts on visible tergite 5 onwards. Males with

Fig. 1. *Allotyphlus karamani* sp. n., habitus, dorsal view.

posterior portion of visible sternite 5 (VII) slightly impressed in middle; sternite 6 (VIII) with median impression and lacking setae, posterior margin with semi-circular median excision (Fig. 2A); tergite IX deeply impressed.

Aedeagus (Figs 2B-C) 0.24 mm long and distinctly asymmetric, with long distal apophysis.

REMARKS. The new species is readily distinguished from other *Morcootyphlus* species only by the different shape of the aedeagus. For the illustrations of aedeagus of other species of the subgenus previously recorded from Greece see Coiffait (1972, 1973), Pace (1983), Assing (2018) and Assing et al. (2019).

NATURAL HISTORY. The material was collected from MSS by a sifting of the soil in a deciduous forest with the northern exposure on the steep slope above a periodical creek. This species lives together with the widespread parthenogenetic *Gynotyphlus perpusillus* (Doderò, 1900). Eleven individuals of late species were collected.

ETYMOLOGY. The new species is named after the zoologist Ivo Karaman from Novi Sad, Serbia, the collector of the species.

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REFERENCES

- ASSING V. 2018. On the Staphylinidae of Crete III. The first records of endogean fauna (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Leptotyphlinae, Aleocharinae). *Linzer biologische Beiträge*. 50(1):7–15.
- ASSING V, Brachat V, Meybohm H. 2019. Monograph of the Staphylinidae of Crete (Greece). Part II. Descriptions of new species (Insecta: Coleoptera). *Beiträge zur Entomologie*. 69(2):239–289.

Fig. 2. *Allotyphlus karamani* sp. n. **A**, visible sternite 5 (VIII), setae on one side omitted; **B**, aedeagus, lateral view; **C**, aedeagus, ventral view. Scale bar, 0.1 mm.

- COIFFAIT H. 1972. Coléoptères Staphylinidae de la région paléarctique occidentale. I. Généralités, sous-familles: Xantholininae et Leptotyphlinae. *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie, Supplément*. 2(2):1–651.
- COIFFAIT H. 1973. Staphylinides endogés nouveaux du Muséum de Genève. *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie*. 3(4):219–224.
- PACE R. 1983. Studio su alcune specie ionico-balcaniche di Leptotyphlinae. *Annalen des Naturhistorischen Museums in Wien, Serie B*. 84:449–461.